

Review Article

Niosomes: Application Of Nanotechnology In Cancer Treatment

Divya M. Sonvane, Gauri S. Salunke, Rakesh C. Thakare , Prasad S. Borade ,
DRX. Ashok Jagdale.

Nandkumar Shinde College of Pharmacy, Aghur, Vaijapur, 423701 Dist - Aurangabad, Maharashtra.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 0 Dec 2023
Accepted: 0 Dec 2023
Published: 04 Dec 2023

Keywords:

Cancer, nanotechnology,
cancer, diagnosis, treatment

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10253631

ABSTRACT

Cancer is a broad term that incorporates various types of tumours that can affect any part of the body. Effective treatment of cancer must include targeted chemotherapeutic agents to the particular target cell with minimal side effects and preventing resistance against the chemotherapeutic agent. Nanotechnology has overcome these challenges. Polymeric [nanoparticles](#) are a class of [nanoparticles](#) in which different polymers are used for encapsulation of the drug. These polymeric nanoparticles are used for targeting particular cancerous cells or tissues by attaching the ligand to it that is having affinity for that particular cell resulting in improvement in stability of the drug. Polymeric nanoparticles are in demand for targeting cancerous tissues with active as well as passive approaches. Exponential use of polymeric nanoparticles for development of chemotherapeutic agents for cancer management has a sophisticated, novel formulation with minimum collateral damage and efficient targeting of therapeutic agents to tumour. In the future, more development of polymers with some therapeutic approaches will impart more use in cancer treatment.

INTRODUCTION

What is cancer?

- Cancer is a large group of diseases with one thing in common: They all happen when normal cells become cancerous cells that multiply and spread.
- Cancer is the second most common cause of death in the U.S. But fewer people are dying of cancer now than 20 years ago.

Early detection and innovative treatments are curing cancer and helping people with cancer live longer. At the same time, medical researchers are identifying independent risk factors linked to developing cancer to help prevent people from developing cancer

What is the difference between a normal cell and a cancerous cell?

*Corresponding Author: Rashid Azeez

Address: Nandkumar Shinde College of Pharmacy, Aghur, Vaijapur, 423701 Dist - Aurangabad, Maharashtra.

Email : divyasonavne007@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

- Normally, cells follow instructions provided by genes. Genes set down rules for cells to follow, such as when to start and stop growing. Cancerous cells ignore the rules that normal cells follow:
- Normal cells divide and multiply in a controlled manner. Cancerous cells multiply uncontrollably.
- Normal cells are programmed to die (apoptosis). Cancerous cells ignore those directions.
- unprotected exposure to UV light, such as sunlight
- infection by certain viruses including H.

What is nanotechnology?

Nanotechnology is the popular term used for the construction and utilization of functional structures with at least one characteristic dimension measured on the nanometer scale. Because of the very small dimensions, most applications of nanobiotechnology in molecular diagnostics fall under the broad category of biochips/microarrays but can be more correctly termed nanochips and nanoarrays. Nanotechnology on a chip is a new paradigm for total chemical analysis systems on a nanoscale. One example of nanotechnology is the use of quantum dots, nanocrystals of cadmium selenide that are 200- to 10,000-atoms wide and coated with zinc sulfide. The size of the dot determines the frequency of light emitted when irradiated with low energy light. This spectral coding technology is expected to open new opportunities in gene expression studies, high throughput screening and medical diagnostics. The initial and most practically useful applications are expected in POC diagnostics where nanotechnology provides advantages over conventional nucleic acid based chips.

TYPES OF CANCER :

- **Breast cancer:** Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer. It mostly affects women and people AFAB. But about 1% of all breast cancer cases affect men and people AMAB.
- **Lung cancer:** Lung cancer is the second most common cancer. There are two types of lung cancer: non-small cell cancer and small cell lung cancer.
- **Prostate cancer:** This cancer affects 1 in 9 men and people AMAB.
- **Colorectal cancer:** Colon cancer and rectal cancer affect different parts of your digestive system.
- **Blood cancers:** Leukemia and lymphoma are the most common blood cancers.

Risk factors:

Certain risk factors may increase your chance of developing cancer. These risk factors can include:

- tobacco use
- high alcohol consumption
- an unhealthy diet, characterized by red and processed meat, sugary drinks and salty snacks, starchy foods, and refined carbohydrates including sugars and processed grains, according to a 2017 review
- a lack of physical activity
- exposure to air pollution
- exposure to radiation

Principles of nanotechnology :

Use of nanotechnology to improve therapeutics is no longer novel, in fact, there has been a steady increase in nanotechnology research as the benefits become more apparent . Currently approved cancer nanomedicines are predominantly liposomal formulations and drug conjugates (protein, polymer, and/or antibody) focused on improving pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics (PK/PD) of the free drug and utilizing passive targeting. There are many clinical studies currently investigating nanomaterials for therapeutic and diagnostic applications, including imaging modalities . Passive targeting for tumours

is based upon the enhanced permeation and retention (EPR) effect, where NPs can preferentially accumulate within tumour vasculature. Many tumours have leaky blood vessels with apertures suitable for NPs to pass through and accumulate within the tumour tissue. However, the EPR effect is not the end-all solution: passive targeting does not eliminate drug action in healthy tissues nor the side effects that accompany systemic distribution. There are physiological obstacles that prevent NPs from reaching their target, even without a diseased state, and can become even more complex to navigate for cancer patients. Protein and lipid adsorption, blood flow rate, coronas, and phagocytic cells can reduce stability and delivery capability. Interstitial pressure and extracellular matrices can also limit access to a tumour. Differences in cancer types can further complicate these issues, presenting a need to optimize formulation according to each kind. First-generation nanomedicines have greatly improved pharmacokinetic (PK) profile, solubility, bioavailability, and stability of major cancer therapeutics. With the growing availability of technology and information, nanomaterials can broaden into new territory to incorporate highly specialized design and function. This enables the next generation of nanomedicine to incorporate combination therapies, specific targeting, triggered drug release, gene therapy, novel immunotherapy approaches, radiation, and multi-modal therapies. Furthermore, as scientific insights elucidate cancer initiation and survival mechanisms, nanotechnology will be a critical asset for improving diagnostics and bioimaging to halt metastasis. Drugs can have vastly different biodistributive properties and relative concentrations, so it can be difficult to optimize dose coordination for combination therapies, and is further complicated by vast physiological variations in different types of cancer and amongst individual patients. Co-delivery of synergistic

drugs within a single carrier can greatly improve synergistic potential as complementary action can occur in a coordinated fashion. Nanomaterials such as lipid-based, polymeric, inorganic, carbon-based, bio macromolecules, and hydrogel can properly formulate multiple therapeutics with highly different chemical properties. Multiple drugs may be engineered to be released simultaneously or in specific sequence depending on kinetics and mechanism of action, with drug release occurring through degradation of the carrier, drug desorption, diffusion through the nanoparticle matrix, or by triggered release. Specific targeting utilizes a nanocarrier or drug conjugate tethered with specific molecules that have high affinity for cancerous cells and lower affinity for healthy cells, lowering the likelihood of systemic toxicity. Antibody drug conjugates currently improve targeting, but targeted delivery of a nanocarrier may incorporate a higher dosage of drug and typically have more versatility for targeting modes using dynamic nanomaterials. For example, doxorubicin (DOX)-loaded immunoliposomes decorated with epidermal growth factor (EGF) to target EGF receptors (EGFR) are currently in clinical trials (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT03603379). Specific targeting can also be utilized for tumour imaging, for example, probes targeting somatostatin receptors overexpressed in neuroendocrine tumours and activated only within the tumour microenvironment (TME) [68]. Nanocarriers must be able to protect the cargo from degradation, achieve prolonged circulation, avoid the reticuloendothelial system uptake, and efficiently deliver to the target cells. Therefore, engineering of the nano formulations requires proper selection of carrier materials, choice of ligand, and optimal density of ligand on the nanocarrier's surface. Certain therapies require intracellular delivery and while others utilize cellular membrane diffusion, so specific

mechanism of action further plays a critical role in optimizing nano formulation. Under particular circumstances, targeting constituents of the TME can be sufficient to see improved drug efficacy and specificity . In addition to specific targeting, nanotechnology can improve therapeutic specificity through stimuli-responsive activation. Release of drugs occurs under precise chemical, biological, or physical conditions found within tumour environment or cancerous cells to limit off-target effects . Nanocarriers may be designed to release drugs under specific pH, glucose levels, specific enzymes, oxidative/reductive conditions, and ion concentration, or by external stimulation such as radiation, electric and magnetic fields, and hyperthermia . These same modalities may be exploited for imaging and diagnostic purposes as well, such as utilizing magnetic particles for MRI tumour imaging or theranostics applications. pH-responsive peptide-based NPs were recently engineered to morph into fibrils within the TME where they exhibited strong fluorescent signals and enhanced photodynamic therapy . Intrinsic properties of certain nanomaterials are ideal for bioimaging, multi-modal therapies, and molecular detection for diagnostics . Fluorescent NPs have shown to be effective alternatives to traditional dyes, demonstrating high stability and decreased photobleaching . Gd-based NPs have shown great utility as MRI and CT contrast agents and as radiosensitizers due to their paramagnetic property and high X-ray attenuation coefficient . Gold NPs are ideal for creating highly selective, versatile, and sensitive biosensors, capable of optical and electrical detection, surface plasmon resonance, and fluorescence resonance energy transfer . Nanomaterials can enable early detection of circulating tumour cells (CTCs) from peripheral blood, as was shown using magnetic NPs functionalized with polyethyleneimine/protein corona or in a separate study, tannic acid . The vast range of nanotechnology applications can

drastically improve cancer therapies and diagnostics, and this review provides an overview of current clinical applications and forthcoming technologies

Cancer treatments using nano–technology:

As Nano–scaled dimensions have the ability to enhance delivery of molecule of drug and under rate the side effects of drug and drug carrier, they are used as treatment of conditions like different stages of tumour, cancer, microbial infections, gene therapy and chronic hyper glycemia . The main superiorities of this model of treatment are these particles act as contrast medium i.e. enhances the visibility of blood vessels for diagnostic purpose and biosensors, cell culture, magnetic nano–particles and enhance renewal and growth of tissue. Nanostructures are being highly valued in the field of tumour imaging. Small size of nano particles, due to their EPR (enhanced permeability and retention effects), can invade tumours and leak into abnormal tumour blood vessels and accumulate in tumour tissues. In Pharmaceutical development, nanotechnology proved to be the most important milestone. In human, Nano particles demonstrate superlative activity against cancer *in vitro*.

Nano–tubes:

Nano–tubes possess great firmness and strength, produce heat and destroy surrounding tumour cells by absorbing Near (IR) infra red light rays. Indium–111 radio nucleus, a label carbon nano–tube has been inspected to destroy tumour cells. The SWNT – (Single– Walled–Carbon Nano Tubes) have been investigated as new transporting agent *in vitro*. SWNTs can efficiently transport various bimolecular substances inside human cells like therapeutic agents, amino acids, proteins, DNA and intervening RNA , by means of endocytosis. Carbon nano–tubes have the intrinsic (NIR) near infra red light absorption property which is useful in destroying cancer spots and Near–IR (infra–red) photoluminescence property

which is used for cell visualizing and exploring, *in vitro*. Physicians can perform precise molecular and cellular intervention through nano-robotic devices. Medical Nano robots have been recommended for gene technological applications in pharmaceutical studies, clinical science, and in modern dentistry. It can also be applied for reoccurring atherosclerosis, boosting breathing ability, allowing near-immediate homeostasis, boosting immune system, substituting sequences of DNA in cells, healing brain damage and fixing gross cellular distress which may have occurred due to unchangeable process or by storage of biological tissues at low temperature. Active and passive are two models which are being used for targeting nano-scaled particles to specific site of tumour. Active is all about connecting the ligands to tumour specific nanoparticles. The basic and characteristic mass of nanoparticles and the distinctive ability of tumour vascular system are the advantage of passive targeting.

Quantum dots:

Quantum dots are shiny new semiconductor nano-crystals,³⁰ their radiation is firm, solid, time-honoured, and inextinguishable and they are being used in many different researches related to cancer cure and therapy.³¹ A nano-particle with biomolecules attached to its surface or conjugation of the quantum dots is regulated to target many biological markers.

Nano shells:

The Gold Nano shells, developed by West and Halas, is an additional appealing way to detect and treat cancer. These gold shells are intended to attack melanocytes by a film of melanocyte stimulating hormone (MSH). These Nano-spheres are made steady and then particularly absorbed by tumour cells via receptor-mediated endocytosis. It was proclaimed through a model of subcutaneous colon cancer that organized administration of gold nano-particles of 33nm in size will initiate it's

binding to tumour necrosis factor (TNF) gathered in tumours.

Nano-bombs:

Nano-bombs can destruct cancerous cells, tumour cells and vessel system around abnormal cells that nourish those diseased cells, but these bombs can be harmful for surrounding healthy cells if used in more than normal amount. Contrast agent super paramagnetic nano-particles are used to enhance the contrast to characterize status of lymph node in medical imaging in humans like patients with fibro adenomas, cancer in respiratory tract, Prostate cancer, endometrial cancer and cervical cancer. Iron oxide super paramagnetic are captivating as they have higher responsiveness to magnetism unlike gadolinium, a traditional MR contrast agent.

Liposomal nanoparticles as a targeted drug-delivery system:

(a-j) Illustration to clarify the described drug-delivery systems of various nanoparticles (NPs).

- (a) Liposomal nanoparticle;
- (b) solid lipid nanoparticle;
- (c) gold nanoparticle;
- (d) nano diamond;
- (e) magnetic nanovector;²²⁰
- (f) carbon nanotube;
- (g) quantum dot nanocarrier;
- (h) polymeric nanoparticle;
- (i) dendrimer nanoparticle;
- (j) virus-mediated nanocarrier.²

Applications of nanotechnology in cancer therapeutics:

cancer progression has become a focal point in developing new drug therapies, but new drug development costs billions of dollars and takes over a decade from development to FDA approval. Conventional cancer therapies remain the first-line treatment for most cancers, and drug discovery is constantly evolving and shifting toward cancer-specific targets. Cytotoxic and targeted therapies can select for drug resistance, therefore making complete eradication of cancer cells nearly impossible. Chemotherapy drugs include alkylating agents and antibiotics to induce DNA damage, antimetabolites, through alterations in drug metabolism, changes in mitotic inhibitors, and topoisomerase inhibitors to efflux/influx, hyper-activated repair pathways, signal interfere with cellular replication. Despite the high transduction re-routing, and mutated drug targets. efficacy of traditional chemotherapies, patients suffer because of their non-specificity. Methods for overcoming drug resistance include Traditional multiple therapeutics, combination chemotherapies are highly toxic to cancerous cells, chemoradiotherapy, and personalized medicine. Co-but systemically affect healthy cells and induce harsh administration of drugs with different molecular side effects for patients. There are specific signalling targets can help modulate cancer cell mutations and networks known to promote and sustain cancer, and a possibly halt the cancer adaptation process. Effective multitude of inhibitors currently exist and are under combinations have been found where a drug can development to target enzymes within these pathways heighten or re-introduce sensitivity of the cancer cells. Various inhibitors of tyrosine kinases, cyclin-dependent kinases, poly ADP-ribose polymerases, and proteasomes comprise the majority small-clinical trials. However, limitations exist for molecule drugs currently used in the clinic as targeted combination treatments largely due to different therapies. Tumour growth and proliferation is fuel by PK/PD properties and disjointed uptake of the components found in the TME such as immune and complementary drugs, which reduces their efficacy inflammatory cells, blood and lymphatic endothelial and synergistic action. Co-delivery of anti-cancer cells, cancer associated fibroblasts (CAFs), and bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells within a single nanocarrier can alleviate Protein these issues and increase the therapeutic index. In synthesis, glucose metabolism, and other key components of cell survival are often hyper-activated approved VYXEOS, a liposomal formulation of in the PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathways, often re-routing cytarabine and daunorubicin at a fixed 5:1 molar signals in response to initial therapies. The ratio, for the treatment of adults with newly diagnosed RAS/RAF/ MEK/ERK pathway initiates cell acute myeloid leukemia (AML) with myelodysplasia-proliferation, differentiation, and development, thus related changes and therapy-related AML. The multiple mutations are commonly found here across synergistic molar ratio of daunorubicin and many cancer types. Mutation in RAS proteins is the cytarabine has been shown to enhance the killing of one of the most commonly found in human cancers, leukemia cells in vitro and in murine models. In and Sotorasib is the first KRAS targeting drug to preclinical studies, VYXEOS liposomes were receive FDA approval. Mutations in EGFRs also preferentially taken up by leukemia cells than by contribute to oncogenesis, and there are normal bone marrow cells in a murine model approximately 14 EGFR-tyrosine kinase inhibitors Furthermore, the liposomes were strategically (TKIs) on the market and/or in clinical trials. Targeting these pathways and factors responsible for leukemic cells compared to the expression in normal

bone marrow cells. This is a promising treatment option, but the need persists for more innovative technologies to combat drug resistance and therapy-related toxicities.

Use of nanotechnology in cancer treatment via gene therapy:

Gene therapy can be defined as the transfer of genetic material to the cells of an individual, in order to ensure a targeted molecular intervention and achieve a higher level of specific action than conventional cytotoxic chemotherapy. Recently, the gene-silencing technique has gained much popularity. There are three major nucleic acid-based gene silencing molecules viz antisense oligo deoxyribonucleic acids, siRNA, and micro RNA. Despite so much promise of gene therapy, a number of difficulties remain to be conquered; the most important is the need for more efficient gene-delivery systems. The success of a gene therapy largely depends upon the activity induced by the target genes and the efficiency of gene delivery resulting from the combined effects of the delivery vector and the applied delivery route. Various NPs have been investigated for gene delivery, including GNPs, silver NPs, CNTs, liposomes, polymersomes, and polyplexes. Use of NPs enables targeting of tumour tissue through the EPR effect in gene

Applications	Without use of nanotechnology	With use of nanotechnology
Diagnosis	Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC), biopsy, Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH), immune histo - chemistry used for diagnosis. Early detection is not possible Only <i>in vitro</i> detection is possible. Real time detection is not possible	Quantum dots and Raman probe can be used for diagnosis. Early detection is possible. <i>In vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> detection is possible. Real time detection is also possible.
Imaging	X-ray, CT (Computerized tomography) scan, Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Positron emission tomography (PET scan) and Ultrasonography can be used.	Quantum dots can be used UCM (Ultrasound contrast medium) ultrasonography can be used. Very early detection of neo vascularization is possible. Imaging, targeting, delivering and monitoring is possible.
Early detection of cancer	Cytology, and biopsy are used. FNAC	Vital optical imaging is possible. Inexpensive mass screening is possible.
Drug delivery	Oral, intramuscular, intravenous, intra-arterial drug delivery is possible.	Targeted delivery is possible to deliver small dose, low systemic toxicity and better and faster responses.

Kim et al reported a mannosylated chitosan NP-mediated cytokine gene-delivery system for cancer immunotherapy. Recently, thiolated chitosan NPs as a delivery system for antisense therapy has also been reported in T47D breast cancer cells. A nanosized immune liposome-based delivery complex was also reported, which preferentially targets and delivers molecules useful in gene medicine, including plasmid DNA and antisense oligonucleotides to tumour cells. This tumour-targeting NP delivery vehicle can

also deliver siRNA to both primary and metastatic cells. A gene-delivery vehicle, nonviral vector DOTAP: cholesterol has been suggested as an effective systemic gene delivery vector that efficiently delivers tumour-suppressor genes to disseminated lung tumours. A promising role of novel nonviral gene carrier heparin-polyethyleneimine (HPEI) NP-mediated ms-T34 A in C-26 colon carcinoma therapy was also reported. PEI-derived NPs such as poly (ϵ -caprolactone)-pluronic-poly(ϵ -caprolactone)-grafted PEI (PCFC-g-PEI), folic acid-PCFC-

isophorone diisocyanates PEI and HPEI are reported as gene-therapy delivery systems for renal cell carcinoma. It has been reported in the literature that QDs may also function as gene-delivery vehicles if modified with lipofectamine, encapsulated in poly(maleic-anhydride-alt-1-decene), surface-modified with di methylamino propylamine and poly(maleic-anhydride-alt-1-decene) coated. QDs have been reported as siRNA delivery vehicles and exhibit up to a 20-fold increase in silencing effect and a sixfold decrease in toxicity compared with other common delivery agents. Gene delivery could also be achieved by the use of CNTs.² They are a good nonviral vector for gene therapy, and can cross the cell membrane by an endocytosis process. CNTs are promising vectors for gene and protein, for which they have shown much greater fluorescent activity of protein and DNA when conjugated to single walled NTs. The delivery of siRNA for treatment of tumour cells using functionalized MWCNTs and liposomes showed that the siRNA delivered via MWCNTs achieved significant inhibition of tumour growth. Dendrimers have also been reported to enter tumours and carry either chemotherapeutic agents or genetic therapeutics. They could be conjugated to fluorochromes and possess the ability to enter into cells. They can then be detected within the cell in a manner compatible with sensing apparatus for evaluation of physiologic changes. DNA-assembled poly amidoamine dendrimer clusters for cancer cell-specific targeting were also reported. Dendrimer-5-fluorouracil (5FU) conjugates were prepared by acetylation, and upon hydrolysis release free 5FU, thus minimizing the toxicity of 5FU. In earlier studies, researchers have shown that cisplatin encapsulated in dendrimer polymers has increased efficacy and is comparatively less toxic. Novel gene silencing strategy in gene therapy involving the use of siRNA can be conjugated to phospholipid-functionalized SWNTs using a

cleavable disulfide linker, resulting in efficient gene silencing and subsequent death of the targeted cell.¹⁴⁹ Amino-functionalized MWNT-siRNA complexes have shown successful suppression of tumour and prolonged survival in lung tumour in animal model. CNTs cationic functionalized with PEI have been shown to be capable of complexing with siRNA and significantly increasing silencing activity and cytotoxicity. A highly efficient, low-toxic, and specifically targeting gene-delivery vector (H1) was also reported. Peritumoral injection of H1/pIL-2 NPs displayed effective antitumour potential. Researchers have derived PEI-coated virus-like particles from an adeno-associated virus type 2 delivery system for potential therapy of breast cancer.

Need for nanotechnology in the medical field:

Nanotechnology and nano drugs discoveries are so vast and wide ranging. Nanomedicine has undergone impressive modifications, pushing the drug to a new level with significant healthcare outcomes. There is a need to study the significant capabilities of nanotechnology in healthcare. In medicine, extensive research is ongoing into best practices and methodologies, including nephrology, cardiovascular disease therapeutic gene, and cancer therapy. There is a significant development in the traditional treatment, and the quality of nanoparticles and nanotechnology have improved and shown encouraging results. Gene therapy has also taken advantage of nano drugs. Several investigations focused on the applications of viral vectors believed to be systems for medication delivery. Nanobots targeting specific cancer cells to smart tablets send data back to researchers to ensure patients receive their treatment correctly. Nanotechnology offers the potential for in-vitro diagnosis by substituting existing procedures for more economical alternatives that are easier to utilise. Nanoparticles can operate as molecular imaging agents within

those devices and input cancer-related genetic alterations and tumour cell functional features. Further, functional nanotechnology-based coatings frequently include the following nanomaterials, depending on the desired function: titanium dioxide, silicon dioxide, carbon black, iron oxide, zinc oxide, and silver. Instruments and procedures enhance physio-chemical characterisation assessments, safety, and effectiveness of nanomaterials and nano surfaces integrated into medical device engineering. Scientists play a crucial part in creating goods that include novel materials, sensors, and energy storage systems.

Implications and Future Directions:

Nanoparticles provide opportunities for designing and tuning properties that are not possible with other types of therapeutic drugs, and have shown a bright future as a new generation of cancer therapeutics. Furthermore, the development of multifunctional nanoparticles may eventually render nanoparticles able to detect and kill cancer cells simultaneously. Although there are certain critical questions and many challenges remaining for the clinical development of nanoparticles, as more clinical data are available, further understanding in nanotechnology will certainly lead to the more rational design of optimized nanoparticles with improved selectivity, efficacy, and safety. The therapeutic benefits of nanotechnology and future advancements could make them a therapeutic potential to be applied in other disease conditions. These may include ischemic stroke and rheumatoid arthritis which would require targeted delivery of a suitable pharmacologic agent at the affected site.

CONCLUSION:

Nanotechnology allows targeted drug delivery in affected organs with minimal systemic toxicities due to their specificities. However, as with other therapeutic options, nanotechnology is not completely devoid of toxicities and comes with

few challenges with its use including systemic and certain organ toxicities, hence, causing setbacks with their clinical applications. Given the limitations with nanotechnology, more advancements must be done to improve drug delivery, maximize their efficacy while keeping the disadvantages to the minimum. By improving the interactions between the physicochemical properties of the nanomaterials employed, safer and more efficacious derivatives for diagnosis and treatment can be made available for cancer management.

REFERENCES

1. Conclusion and Future Prospective of Polymeric Nanoparticles for Cancer Therapy - Rahul Shukla , Mayank Handa, Siva B. Lokesh , Munindar Ruwali , Kanchan Kohli, Prashant Kesharwani.<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-816963-6.00018-2>
2. Application Of Nanotechnology in Cancer - Hirendra N. Banerjee, M.D., Ph.D.1,* Mukesh Verma, Ph.D.2 www.tcrt.org.in
3. Applications of nanotechnology in medical field - Abid Haleema , Mohd Javaida,* , Ravi Pratap Singhb , Shanay Rabc , Rajiv Sumand : <https://www.keaipublishing.com/en/journals/global-health-journal>
4. Advances of Cancer Therapy by Nanotechnology - Xu Wang, Ph.D.1 Yiqing Wang, Ph.D.2 Zhuo (Georgia) Chen, Ph.D.1 Dong M. Shin, M.D.
5. Nanotechnology-based approaches in anticancer research – Nasimudeen R Jabir, Shams Tabrez, Ghulam Md Ashraf, Shazi Shakil, Ghazi A Damanhoury & Mohammad A Kamal : <https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/dijn20>
6. Cancer nanotechnology: current status and perspectives - Jessica A. Kemp¹ and Young Jik Kwon

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40580-021-00282-7>

7. Application of Nanotechnology in Cancer Diagnosis and Therapy - Cancan Jin ,

Kankai Wang , Anthony Oppong-Cyebi ,
and liangnan.Hu

HOW TO CITE: Divya M. Sonvane, Gauri S. Salunke, Rakesh C. Thakare , Prasad S. Borade , DRX. Ashok Jagdale. *Nandkumar Shinde College of Pharmacy, Aghur, Vaijapur, 423701 Dist - Aurangabad, Maharashtra.*, *Int. J. in Pharm. Sci.*, 2023, Vol 1, Issue 12, 21-32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10253631>

